

The easternmost nesting record of a Leatherback Turtle, *Dermochelys coriacea* (Testudines: Dermochelyidae), in Cuba

El registro más oriental de anidación de un Tinglado, *Dermochelys coriacea* (Testudines: Dermochelyidae), en Cuba

Julián Matos-Navarro¹
Seriocha Amaro-Valdés^{2*}

¹Elemento Natural Destacado Maisí-Caleta, Empresa Nacional para la Protección de la Flora y la Fauna, Municipio Maisí, CP 99320, Guantánamo, Cuba.

²Instituto de Ecología y Sistemática, Carretera Varona, No. 11835, e/ Oriente y Lindero, Reparto Parajón, Municipio Boyeros, CP 10800, La Habana, Cuba.

*Corresponding author: amaro.seriocha@gmail.com

Editorenjefe: Alex M. Cubas-Rodríguez ► **Recibido** 10 Julio 2025 ► **Aceptado** 10 Octubre 2025 ► **Publicado** 31 Diciembre 2025

Ref. bibliográfica: Matos-Navarro, J., Castillo-Santiesteban, R. & Amaro-Valdés, S. 2025. The easternmost nesting record of a Leatherback Turtle, *Dermochelys coriacea* (Testudines: Dermochelyidae), in Cuba. *Scientia hondurensis*. 5(2): 73–79. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18099465.

ABSTRACT

We report the first documented nesting event of the Leatherback Turtle, *Dermochelys coriacea* (Vandelli, 1761), in the Outstanding Natural Element Maisí-Caleta Protected Area, Maisí Municipality, Guantánamo Province, Cuba. On 23 May 2024, a female Leatherback Turtle deposited 77 yolked eggs in the sand of Playa La Pluma. After an *in situ* incubation period of 51 days, 48 hatchlings successfully reached the sea, resulting in an emergence success of 62.33%. In addition, we summarize the very limited number of confirmed and unconfirmed records of Leatherback Turtle nesting within the Cuban Archipelago.

Key words: Eastern Cuba, Outstanding Natural Element Maisí-Caleta, sea turtle, West Indies

RESUMEN

Registramos el primer evento documentado de anidación de un Tinglado, *Dermochelys coriacea* (Vandelli, 1761), en el Área Protegida Elemento Natural Destacado Maisí-Caleta, municipio Maisí, provincia de Guantánamo, Cuba. El 23 de mayo de 2024, una hembra de Tinglado depositó 77 huevos con vitelo en la arena de Playa La Pluma. Tras un período de incubación *in situ* de 51 días, 48 crías alcanzaron exitosamente el mar, lo que representa un éxito de emergencia del 62,33%. Asimismo, se compilan los muy escasos registros, tanto confirmados como no confirmados, de anidación del Tinglado en el archipiélago cubano.

Palabras clave: Antillas, Cuba Oriental, Elemento Natural Destacado Maisí-Caleta, tortuga marina.

INTRODUCTION

Five of the six species of sea turtles that occur the Wider Caribbean Region (WCR), which encompasses the Caribbean Sea plus the coasts of Bermuda and the Gulf of Mexico, have been reported in the Cuban Archipelago (Eckert & Eckert 2019). Of these, four have been reported nesting on Cuban beaches: Green (*Chelonia mydas* [Linnaeus, 1758]), Loggerhead (*Caretta caretta* [Linnaeus, 1758]), Hawksbill (*Eretmochelys imbricata* [Linnaeus, 1766]), and Leatherback (*Dermochelys coriacea* [Vandelli, 1761]). Although all these species are threatened with extinction at both regional and global levels (Amaro-Valdés 2012; IUCN 2019), only 31 of the 43 nations and territories within the WCR, have enacted long-term, comprehensive measures for protecting sea turtles (Dow Piniak & Eckert 2011). Furthermore, only Bermuda, Cuba, Saint Eustatius, and the United States of America have reported adequate enforcement of sea turtle protection laws (Dow Piniak & Eckert 2011).

Although Cuba has enacted comprehensive legal protection for sea turtles, some species remain rare in its waters and nesting beaches. In particular, the Leatherback Turtle has been documented in-water in both the northern and southern regions of the Cuban shelf since the second half of the 19th century (Gundlach 1867). However, sightings of this species in Cuba, which have been reported for over 112 years, have remained sparse (Buide 1985). Therefore, Leatherbacks are still considered an uncommon species in the Cuban Archipelago, although the Cuban waters serve as an important migration corridor for populations of this species from other Caribbean regions (Moncada Gavilán 2014; Ruiz Plasencia 2019a, b). Similarly, nesting reports of Leatherback Turtles in Cuba are rare and poorly documented, despite the implementation of comprehensive monitoring of sea turtle nesting beaches over the past 16 years (Moncada Gavilán *et al.* 2011; Eckert & Eckert 2019). We report a new nesting event of the Leatherback Turtle in Cuba.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At 2350 h on 23 May 2024, we found tracks left by a female Leatherback Turtle in the sand of Playa La Pluma, Outstanding Natural Element (ONE) Maisí-Caleta, Maisí Municipality, Guantánamo Province, Cuba (20°22'52" N, 74°13'31" W). Although we did not see the turtle, the nest was marked and monitored daily by conservation workers. The *in situ* incubation period for the eggs was 51 days, with hatchlings emerging on July 13 (24 hatchlings), July 14 (17 hatchlings), and July 15 (7 hatchlings) (fig. 1A–D). A total of 48 hatchlings reached the sea; emergence success of 62.33% [emergence success = (number of hatchlings that came out of nest/number of yolked eggs laid) × 100].

Figure 1. Hatchlings Leatherback Turtles (*Dermodochelys coriacea*) on Playa La Puma, Outstanding Natural Element Maisí-Caleta, Maisí Municipality, Guantánamo Province, Cuba. **A.** Hatchlings begin to emerge from the nest. **B.** The number of hatchlings emerged increases. **C.** A group of hatchlings heading to the sea. **D.** The last hatchling entering the sea. / Crías de Tinglado (*Dermodochelys coriacea*) en Playa La Puma, Elemento Natural Destacado Maisí-Caleta, municipio Maisí, provincia Guantánamo, Cuba. **A.** Las crías comienzan a emerger del nido. **B.** Aumenta el número de crías que emergen. **C.** Un grupo de crías se dirige al mar. **D.** La última cría entra al mar. Photographs taken by Radielvis Castillo-Santiesteban (A) and Julián Matos-Navarro (B, C & D).

After the last hatchling emerged, we examined the nest and found five dead hatchlings; hatching success of 68.83% [hatching success = (number of hatchlings / number of yolked eggs laid) \times 100]. Of 77 yolked eggs laid, 24 failed to hatch and three smaller eggs without yolk failed to develop. These data from Playa La Puma are consistent with those reported for this species in the literature, considering that *Dermodochelys coriacea* has the lowest hatching and emergence success values among sea turtles (Chacón Chaverri 1999; Hilterman & Goverse 2007; Velásquez *et al.* 2010).

This was the first record of a Leatherback Turtle nesting on ONE Maisí-Caleta and the easternmost record for a Leatherback nest in Cuba. The photographs are the first illustration of the hatchlings of this species in the Cuban Archipelago. Only two other confirmed nesting events have been documented in Cuba: one in June 2003 at Varadero beach, Matanzas Province (Pereira González *et al.* 2006) and another at Cayo Campos, Los Canarreos Archipelago, in the summer of 2004 (date unspecified; Moncada Gavilán 2006). In both cases, hatchlings were observed.

Additionally, four unconfirmed records of potential Leatherback Turtle nesting

events in Cuba were poorly documented, often relying on personal communications by fishermen, guards, or soldiers, with some lacking details on location, date, and possibly accurate identification of the species (Alberts *et al.* 2001; Moncada Gavilán 2014). The localities of these unconfirmed Leatherback Turtle nesting events were the Península de Guanahacabibes, Pinar del Río Province; Cayo Blanco and Cayo Caguama in the Jardines de la Reina Archipelago (Moncada Gavilán & Rodríguez 1996); and Guantánamo Bay (Alberts *et al.* 2001; Alberts 2003; fig. 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of unconfirmed and confirmed nesting records of the Leatherback Turtle (*Dermochelys coriacea*) on the Cuban Archipelago. Numbers refer to the following locations and citations:

[Distribución de los registros de anidación confirmados y no confirmados de Tinglado (*Dermochelys coriacea*) en el Archipiélago Cubano. Los números corresponden a las siguientes localidades y citas:] (1)

- Península de Guanahacabibes, Pinar del Río Province (Moncada Gavilán & Rodríguez 1996); (2) Cayo Blanco, Jardines de la Reina Archipelago (Moncada Gavilán & Rodríguez 1996); (3) Cayo Caguama, Jardines de la Reina Archipelago (Moncada Gavilán & Rodríguez 1996); (4) Guantánamo Bay (Alberts *et al.* 2001); (5) Varadero, Matanzas Province (Pereira González *et al.* 2006); (6) Cayo Campos, Los Canarreos Archipelago (Moncada Gavilán 2006); (7) Playa La Pluma, Outstanding Natural Element Maisí-Caleta, Guantánamo Province (this report); insert: location of Playa La Pluma in Maisí-Caleta Protected Area. Map credit: Joaquín Hernández.

Monitoring of sea turtle nesting beaches on the Península de Guanahacabibes has been ongoing for more than 21 years, with no sightings of nesting Leatherbacks (Ibarra Martín *et al.* 1999; Azanza-Ricardo *et al.* 2015; Eckert & Eckert 2019). However, records of turtles in the water (i.e., not nesting) exist for both Guantánamo Bay and Jardines de la Reina Archipelago (Alberts *et al.* 2001; Ruiz Plasencia 2019a). Lacking confirmation or new observations, the four nesting records we pointed out as unconfirmed have not been considered valid by several authors (Moncada Gavilán *et al.* 2011; Eckert & Eckert 2019; this report).

The nesting record reported here is comparable to the few other confirmed cases in Cuba and remains a rare event. Gravid females of this sea turtle species typically select nesting beaches characterized as deep, clean, high-energy sites with either a deep-water oceanic approach or a shallow-water approach bordered by mud banks but lacking coral or rocky formations (Eckert *et al.* 2012). However, the absence of obstructions in the approach appears to be more critical than the absolute depth (Eckert *et al.* 2012). Therefore, such events will likely remain uncommon as Cuban beaches typically have gentle and shallow slopes and nearby coral reefs can deter nesting Leatherback Turtles (Moncada Gavilán 2014).

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

JM-N and **RC-S** monitoring the nest area and collected the field data; **SA-V** and **JM-N** analyzed the data, wrote and reviewed the text.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Roberis Navarro Arias (ONE Maisí-Caleta, Guantánamo) for her collaboration during the monitoring of the nest, and Joán Hernández (Refugio de Vida Silvestre Cayo Francés, Villa Clara, Cuba) for the map. Robert Powell (Avila University, Kansas City, USA) and Félix G. Moncada Gavilán (Centro de Investigaciones Pesqueras, La Habana, Cuba) provided some valuable literature. We also grateful to reviewers for their thoughtful comments and suggestions

LITERATURE CITED:

Alberts, A.C., Grant, T.D., Gerber, G.P., Comer, K.E., Tolson, P.J., Lemm, J.M. & Boyer, D. (2001) *Critical reptile species management on the U.S. Naval Base, Guantánamo Bay, Cuba*. Final Report to the United States Navy for Project No. 62470-00-M-5219, Zoological Society of San Diego, California, USA.

Alberts, A.C. (2003) Conserving the remarkable reptiles of Guantánamo Bay. Pp. 67–73. *In*: Henderson, R.W. & Powell, R. (Eds.), *Islands and the Sea: Essays on Herpetological Exploration in the West Indies*. Society for the Study of Amphibians and Reptiles, Contributions to Herpetology, volume 20, Ithaca, New York, USA. 312 pp.

Amaro-Valdés, S. (2012) *Lista Roja de la Fauna Cubana*. Editorial AMA, La Habana, Cuba. 171 pp.

Azanza-Ricardo, J., Gerhartz-Muro, J.L., Forneiro Martín-Viaña, Y. & Moncada Gavilán, F.[G.]. (2015) Efectividad del monitoreo de la anidación de tortugas marinas para determinar el éxito reproductivo en playas del sur de Cuba. *Latin American Journal of Aquatic Research*, **43**(3):548–556. <https://doi.org/10.3856/vol43-issue3-fulltext-16>

Buide, M.S. (1985) *Reptiles de Cuba*. Editorial Gente Nueva, La Habana, Cuba. 86 pp.

Chacón Chaverri, D. (1999) Anidación de la tortuga *Dermochelys coriacea* (Testudines: Dermochelyidae) en playa Gandoca, Costa Rica (1990 a 1997). *Revista de Biología Tropical*, **47**(1–2):225–236.

Dow Piniak, W.E. & Eckert, K.L. (2011) Sea turtle nesting habitat in the Wider Caribbean Region. *Endangered Species Research*, **15**:129–141. <https://doi.org/10.3354/esr00375>

Eckert, K.L., Wallace, B.P., Frazier, J.G., Eckert, S.A. & Pritchard, P.C.H. (2012) *Synopsis of the biological data on the Leatherback Sea Turtle* (*Dermochelys coriacea*). U.S. Department of Interior, Fish and Wildlife Service. Biological Technical Publication BTP-R4015-2012, Washington, D.C., USA. 158 pp.

Eckert, K.[L.] & Eckert, A. (2019) *An atlas of sea turtle nesting habitat for the Wider Caribbean Region*. WIDECASST Technical Report No. 19, Godfrey, Illinois, USA.

Gundlach, J. (1867) Revista y catálogo de los reptiles cubanos. *Repertorio Físico-Natural de la Isla de Cuba*, **2**(5):102–119.

Hilterman, M.L. & Goverse, E. (2007) Nesting and nest success of the Leatherback Turtle (*Dermochelys coriacea*) in Suriname, 1999-2005. *Chelonian Conservation and Biology*, **6**(1):87–100.

Ibarra Martín, M.E., Angulo Valdés, J., Espinosa López, G., Pacheco Roberto, J., Moncada Gavilán, F.[G.], Nodarse Andreu, G., & Escobar González, E. (1999) University Project on the study and conservation of Cuban sea turtles. *Marine Turtle Newsletter*, **84**:1–12.

IUCN. (2019) *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species*. Version 2019.2. <https://www.iucnredlist.org>. Consultado el: 22 de mayo de 2025.

Moncada [Gavilán], F.[G.]. (2006) Leatherback nesting in Cuba. *The State of the World's Sea Turtles Report*, **1**:32. <https://seaturtlestatus.org/report/swot-volume-1>

Moncada Gavilán, F.G. (2014) Presencia de la tortuga tinglado (*Dermochelys coriacea*) en Cuba. *Revista Cubana de Investigaciones Pesqueras*, **31**(2):58–63.

Moncada [Gavilán], F.[G.] & Rodríguez, O. (1996) Occasional catch and some biological aspects of *Dermochelys coriacea* in Cuba. Pp. 213–215. In: Keinath, J.A., Barnard, D.E., Musick J.A. & Bell, B.A. (Comps.). *Proceedings of the Fifteenth Annual Symposium on Sea Turtle Biology and Conservation*. NOAA Technical Memorandum NMFS-SEFSC-387, Miami, Florida, USA. 355 pp.

Moncada Gavilán, F.[G.], Nodarse Andreu, G., Azanza[-]Ricardo, J., Medina Cruz, Y. & Forneiro Martín-Viaña, Y. (2011) Principales áreas de anidación de las tortugas marinas en el archipiélago cubano. *Cub@: Medio Ambiente y Desarrollo*, **11**(20). <http://cmad.ama.cu>

Pereira González, Y., Ruiz Urquiola, A., Pérez Bermúdez, E., González Pumariega, M., Ruiz Medina, I., Perdomo Molina, J. & Ibarra Martín, M.E. (2006) ¿La anidación de *Dermochelys coriacea* en el archipiélago cubano es un récord? p. 186. *7th Congress on Marine Sciences Marcuba'2006*. Abstracts, La Habana, Cuba. 224 pp.

Ruiz Plasencia, I. (2019a) Parque Nacional Jardines de la Reina. Pp. 217–218. In: Ruiz, I. (Ed.). *Las áreas protegidas de Cuba*. Centro Nacional de Áreas Protegidas, La Habana, Cuba. 386 pp.

Ruiz Plasencia, I. (2019b) Reserva Ecológica Caletones. Pp. 331–332. In: Ruiz, I. (Ed.). *Las áreas protegidas de Cuba*. Centro Nacional de Áreas Protegidas, La Habana, Cuba. 386 pp.

Velásquez, F., Prieto, A., & González, L. (2010) Estatus, revisión y aspectos reproductivos de la tortuga cardón *Dermochelys coriacea* en Venezuela. *Saber*, **22**(1):25–34.

